

Reversed Phase Thin Layer Chromatographic Behaviour of Some Toxic Metal Ions on Tri-n-butyl Phosphate modified Silica Gel-G Layers in Acetone-Nitric Acid-Water Systems : Quantitative Separation of Lead(II) and Chromium(III) from many Metal Ions

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A systematic chromatographic study of twentyfive toxic metal ions on tri-n-butyl phosphate modified silica gel-G layers using acetone-nitric acid-water systems has been performed. The effect of mole fraction of acetone, nitric acid and water on R_f values has been explained. A number of binary and ternary separations has been achieved on these layers. In some cases, separation of one cation from numerous metal ions is possible. Lead has been quantitatively separated from eighteen toxic metal ions, and chromium from fifteen metal ions.

Significant accumulation of toxic metals in the environment has been the subject of great concern in recent years. Thin layer chromatography has proved to be an important tool for identification and estimation of pollution causing metal ions. However, reversed phase thin layer chromatography gives better resolution since the mobile phase as well as phase modifiers affect the selectivity of a system¹. In order to separate a number of potentially toxic metal ions from other metals, tributyl phosphate (TBP) modified thin layers were used. Quantitative separation of chromium and lead is important since these metals are associated with carcinogenicity². Chromium is usually separated by ion-exchange as Cr^{VI} ³. Procedures for ion-exchange separations of Cr^{III} are rare. Cr^{III} was separated quantitatively as an anionic complex with H_2SO_4 on Dowex-50 WX8 resin in the H^+ -form⁴. It was also separated⁵ in the trivalent state from Fe^{III} and Al^{III} only. Fe^{III} and Al^{III} were eluted with 2% oxalic acid. The desorption of Cr^{III} from the column was difficult and hence it was desorbed after converting it to Cr^{VI} with alkaline sodium peroxide. Nitric acid-acetone-water mixtures in varying proportions were chosen as the mobile phase. Nitric acid facilitates mechanistic studies, since it is known to form very few complexes. Acetone was chosen as it does not solvate ions significantly and hence the discussion of mechanism is simpler.

Results and Discussion

Interesting results were obtained using TBP modified thin layer chromatoplates. The development time ranges from 1 to 2 h depending upon the mobile phase composition. The spots are well-defined and compact. Tailing is reported only in few cases, e.g. Mo^{VI} ($\text{S}_1, \text{S}_8, \text{S}_9, \text{S}_{10}$), Zn^{II} (S_1), Sb^{III} (S_3, S_7), Al^{III} (S_4), Bi^{III} (S_8), Se^{IV} (S_{11}), Fe^{III} (S_{13}) and Ce^{III} (S_9).

In order to check the reproducibility of the results, three

sets of chromatographic plates for each cation were developed. It was observed that the variation does not exceed 10% of the average R_f values. The behaviour of metal ions in terms of R_f values can be explained on the basis of adsorption and precipitation in the network of the support. Hydrolysis and solvent-solvent interaction may also play their role in the sorption behaviour of metal ions. The R_f values for different metal ions are given in Table 1.

The effect of solvent composition on R_f values was studied by drawing R_f vs mole fraction plots. On the basis of these plots the effect of mole fraction of each component in the solvent system can be explained as follows.

Effect of mole fraction of acetone on R_f values : To study the effect of mole fraction of acetone on R_f values, the acetone fraction is continuously increased keeping nitric acid-water ratio constant as in case of solvent systems $\text{S}_1, \text{S}_2, \text{S}_3, \text{S}_4, \text{S}_5$ and S_6 . For $\text{Tl}^{\text{I}}, \text{Se}^{\text{IV}}, \text{Ag}^{\text{I}}, \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}, \text{Be}^{\text{II}}, \text{Al}^{\text{III}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ce}^{\text{III}}$ and Ce^{IV} , we get straight-lines and there is decrease in the R_f values with increase in the mole fraction of acetone. This is probably due to a decrease in the number of H^+ ions competing for the exchange sites. Thus it follows that when the aqueous and non-aqueous solvents are both non-complexing and the $\text{HNO}_3 : \text{H}_2\text{O}$ ratio remains constant, the R_f is almost always dependent on the number of H^+ ions competing for the exchange sites. However, the behaviour of Sn^{IV} and Sb^{III} is different as they give higher R_f values at higher acetone concentrations. This is probably due to the fact that the salts of these metals are very soluble in acetone (solubility for SnCl_4 and SbCl_3 , 56 and 538 g/100 g respectively). In case of $\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ and Cd^{II} , the R_f value is high upto solvent composition S_4 but the value suddenly decreases below 0.5 at the solvent composition S_5 . The R_f value for these cations suddenly decreases when solvent system contains almost 70% acetone. The variation in mobile phase composition

TABLE I— R_f VALUES OF METAL IONS IN HNO_3 : ACETONE : H_2O SYSTEMS HAVING VARYING COMPOSITIONS

Metal ion	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅	S ₁₆
Be ^{II}	0.95	0.88	0.68	0.85	0.90	0.60	0.84	0.95	0.94	0.95	1.0	0.88	0.10	0.50	0.88	0.80
Al ^{III}	0.95	0.98	0.88	T	0.60	0.75	0.90	0.90	0.95	1.00	0.95	0.95	1.00	0.60	0.90	0.82
Cr ^{III}	0.95	0.95	0.98	0.62	0.30	0.92	0.25	0.95	1.00	0.90	0.95	0.60	0.40	0.96	0.98	0.32
Mn ^{II}	0.90	T	0.95	0.92	0.90	0.95	0.95	0.90	0.85	0.82	0.62	0.96	0.42	0.98	0.95	0.25
Fe ^{II}	0.95	0.38	0.65	0.92	0.65	0.60	0.80	0.90	0.95	0.26	0.95	0.99	0.40	0.40	0.45	0.25
Fe ^{III}	0.85	0.64	0.60	0.68	0.45	0.55	0.90	0.90	0.85	0.80	0.98	0.98	T	0.50	1.00	0.65
Co ^{II}	0.92	0.75	0.58	0.60	0.80	0.55	0.90	0.95	0.85	0.96	0.98	1.00	1.00	0.92	0.95	0.95
Ni ^{II}	0.85	0.65	0.65	0.74	0.58	0.65	0.93	0.90	1.00	0.95	0.80	0.95	1.00	0.95	0.95	0.95
Cu ^{II}	0.96	0.90	0.50	0.70	0.60	0.62	0.95	0.95	0.88	0.99	0.88	0.80	0.92	0.95	0.96	0.80
Zn ^{II}	0.95	T	1.00	0.90	0.52	0.85	0.85	0.88	0.92	0.95	0.64	0.98	0.94	0.98	1.00	0.70
As ^{III}	0.52	0.94	0.80	0.60	0.90	0.92	0.95	0.42	0.80	0.98	0.85	0.95	1.00	0.95	0.96	0.88
Se ^{IV}	0.95	0.50	0.90	0.85	0.80	0.83	0.95	0.98	0.95	0.95	T	0.98	0.90	0.98	0.95	0.85
Mo ^{VI}	T	0.60	0.88	0.90	0.90	0.80	0.20	T	T	T	0.55	0.20	0.60	0.52	0.72	0.50
Ag ^I	0.95	0.70	0.75	0.90	0.60	0.72	0.95	0.90	0.90	1.00	0.98	0.82	0.90	0.94	0.98	0.20
Cd ^{II}	0.95	0.68	0.98	0.80	0.20	0.55	0.95	0.95	0.92	0.94	0.85	0.94	0.90	0.86	0.93	0.45
Sn ^{II}	0.62	0.90	0.64	0.55	0.90	0.90	0.00	0.90	0.95	1.00	0.18	0.94	0.40	0.80	0.80	0.65
Sn ^{IV}	0.52	0.95	0.82	0.95	0.92	0.95	0.90	0.90	0.84	1.00	0.15	0.55	0.10	0.30	0.90	0.55
Sb ^{III}	0.30	0.70	T	0.90	1.00	0.75	T	0.30	0.25	0.14	0.08	0.00	0.70	0.68	0.30	0.40
Ce ^{III}	0.80	0.75	0.95	0.76	0.50	0.32	0.95	0.85	T	1.00	0.85	0.98	0.13	0.80	1.00	0.20
Ce ^{IV}	0.70	0.90	0.90	0.68	0.85	0.55	0.85	0.60	0.85	0.65	0.90	0.94	1.00	0.95	0.55	0.95
Hg ₂ ^{II}	0.90	0.90	0.85	0.80	0.88	0.90	0.85	0.85	0.85	0.85	0.69	0.98	0.60	0.80	0.50	0.75
Hg ^{II}	0.95	0.70	0.95	0.98	0.85	0.70	0.80	0.50	0.70	0.40	0.46	0.90	0.80	0.84	1.00	0.60
Tl ^I	0.95	0.97	1.00	0.94	0.50	0.42	0.84	1.00	0.84	0.95	0.95	0.45	0.88	0.95	0.98	0.98
Pb ^{II}	0.25	0.89	0.15	0.05	0.85	0.00	0.30	0.20	0.45	0.15	0.20	0.96	0.20	0.65	0.10	0.12
Bi ^{III}	0.90	0.80	0.60	0.90	0.90	0.60	0.75	T	0.86	0.85	0.80	0.90	0.80	0.80	0.75	0.70

T = Tailing.

does not affect the R_f of Mn^{II} which is very soluble in water and HNO_3 and as such it gives high but constant R_f values in all the solvents studied.

Effect of the mole fraction of HNO_3 on R_f values : When the water : acetone mole ratio remains the same and the HNO_3 acid mole fraction being constantly increased, the curves are quite revealing. The R_f value for Tl^I increases linearly with the mole fraction of HNO_3 . The increased R_f is easily explained in terms of the increase in the number of H^+ ions competing with the cations for the exchange sites. The R_f value of Bi^{III} gradually decreases with increase in HNO_3 concentration. In case of Fe^{II} and Fe^{III}, the R_f value first decreases with an increase in HNO_3 concentration and then becomes almost constant. For Cd^{II}, with an increase in HNO_3 concentration there is constant and high R_f values upto S₁₅ composition, but the value suddenly decreases to 0.5 when the HNO_3 concentration is increased further. For cations like As^{III}, Zn^{II}, Se^{IV}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} there is no significant change in R_f with the change in HNO_3 concentration. Cations like Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Sn^{II}, Sn^{IV},

Sb^{III}, Ce^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Hg₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Mo^{VI}, Ag^I, Be^{II}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III} and Mn^{II} show an irregular behaviour.

Effect of the mole fraction of water on R_f values : Keeping the mole ratio of acetone and nitric acid constant, the mole fraction of water is continuously increased. This results in the increase of the R_f value of Sn^{II}, Sn^{IV}, Ce^{IV}, Mo^{VI}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II}. The R_f values increase linearly with the mole fraction of H_2O . For cations like Sb^{III} and Bi^{III}, a decrease in the R_f value with an increase in the mole ratio of water is observed. This may be due to the hydrolysis of the salts of these cations in the solvent media. Toxicants like Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Se^{IV}, Ag^I, Be^{II}, Al^{III} and Cr^{III} give constant R_f values at all concentrations of water.

Due to preferential adsorption on TBP-modified thin layers, in many cases it was possible to separate one cation from numerous metal ions, e.g. Pb is separated from twenty three metal ions, aluminium being the only interfering metal ion in S₄ (1 : 4 : 1) system. Antimony is clearly separated from all the twenty four cations in S₁₂ (2 : 1 : 1) system.

The accumulative poisonous metal mercury (Hg^{II}) has interference of only Mo^{VI} and Fe^{II} in S_9 (1 : 1 : 4) system.

Cadmium and chromium were separated from nineteen cations in S_5 (1 : 5 : 1) system, the only interfering ions being Fe^{III} , Zn^{II} , Ce^{III} and Tl^{I} . Similarly, it is possible to separate other toxicants as evident from their R_f values. A large number of binary and ternary separations were actually achieved, for example $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}-\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$, $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}-\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}-\text{Al}^{\text{III}}$ or Mn^{II} , $\text{Hg}_2^{\text{II}}-\text{Hg}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}-\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}$, $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}-\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}-\text{Sb}^{\text{III}}$ - Ce^{IV} . Thus tributyl phosphate (TBP) modified layers and nitric acid : acetone : water system as developer are very useful for separating one toxic metal ion from other metal toxicants. The utility of these TBP-modified layers has been demonstrated by the quantitative separation of Pb^{II} and Cr^{III} from a large number of other toxic metal ions. Percentage error for the determination of Pb^{II} (10–100 μg) was found to be $\pm 2\%$ and that for Cr^{III} (2–10 μg) was $\pm 10\%$.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric studies were performed on a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer.

Silica gel-G, tri-n-butyl phosphate (TBP), diphenyl carbazide (DPC), dithiozone and benzene (AnalaR) were used. Other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Standard solutions were in most cases prepared from nitrates/chlorides of the elements. Solutions of multivalent elements with tendencies to hydrolysis were prepared in a little amount of the corresponding acids. Conventional spot test reagents were used for detection purposes⁶.

Preparation of TBP impregnated thin layers : The slurry was prepared by mixing silica gel-G with conductivity water (1 : 3) with stirring for ~5 min and immediately coated on glass plates. The plates were dried first at room temperature and then in an electric oven for 2 h at $100 \pm 5^\circ$. Silica gel-G layers were then impregnated with 20% mixture of tri-n-butyl phosphate in benzene. Benzene was evaporated by heating the plates in an electric oven at $90 \pm 5^\circ$ for 1 h. The plates were stored in dessicator at room temperature and used as such for chromatography.

Procedure :

Qualitative work : The test solution (0.02 ml) containing 2×10^{-6} moles of the ions was applied on TBP modified silica gel-G layers. The plates were allowed to condi-

tion. The solvent ascent was 11 cm in all cases. The R_f values were measured after detection.

Quantitative work : Cr^{III} and Pb^{II} metal ion solutions were loaded with the help of a lambda pipette in the form of a streak. The development was performed in the chosen solvent systems. The ascent was allowed 11 cm from the starting line on the TBP modified layers in all cases. A pilot plate was run simultaneously in order to locate the exact position of the spot on the plate. The areas of Cr^{III} and Pb^{II} were scratched and eluted with 0.5 N H_2SO_4 and $\text{HNO}_3 : \text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (1 : 3 : 1) solutions respectively and filtered. In the filtrate, Cr^{III} was determined spectrophotometrically using diphenylcarbazide⁷. Dithiozone in carbon tetrachloride was used at 535 nm for quantitative determination of Pb^{II} ⁷.

Solvent systems : The following solvents containing HNO_3 : acetone : water in the following proportions were used : S_1 (1:1:1), S_2 (1:2:1), S_3 (1:3:1), S_4 (1:4:1), S_5 (1:5:1), S_6 (1:6:1), S_7 (1:1:2), S_8 (1:1:3), S_9 (1:1:4), S_{10} (1:1:5), S_{11} (1:1:6), S_{12} (2:1:1), S_{13} (3:1:1), S_{14} (4:1:1), S_{15} (5:1:1) and S_{16} (6:1:1).

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